

Advances in Integrated Research

The Influence Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, Return On Assets (ROA), and Wadiah Bonus on Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) with Firm Size as Variable Moderation Period 2015–2023

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine how the acceptance of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, ROA, and wadiah bonus affect CAR (Capital Adequacy Ratio) with Firm Size as a moderating variable. This study uses Islamic bank financial journals from 2018 to 2023. For five years, the purposive sample consisted of 115 samples. Panel Data Regression Analysis and Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) were used, all using Eviews 12. The results showed that ziswaf fund receipts had a large negative impact on CAR in the banking industry from 2018 to 2023. Firm size cannot control the effect of ziswaf fund receipts, ROA, and wadiah bonus on Islamic banking CAR during the period 2018-2023. In order for the research results to represent different banking sectors, future research is expected to use additional moderating variables. In addition, it is expected to use bank samples from various types of banking.

Keywords: Ziswaf Fund, ROA, Wadiah Bonus, Firm Size, CAR

INTRODUCTION

Islamic banking is developing fast. After a number of economic crises, sharia banking gets more attention big. Crisis the world economy in question is crisis 1998 and 2009. Second crisis This has a large impact on countries in the Asian region, including Indonesia. A field study conducted in Amman, Jordan for two years (2007–2009), found that the global economic crisis had more negative impact on conventional banks than Sharia banking.. This matter can be achieved Because Islamic principles make method investment This is more moral and less risky compared to with conventional banks. Scenario has open room more acceptance Good to Islamic finance in general and Islamic banking in particular and provides an alternative to conventional (Sari et al., 2020).

ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds (Zakat, Infaq, Alms, and Waqf) are funds collected from various sources, including individuals and organizations, for Then used in various related activities with social and economic public interest. ZISWAF has the objective of increasing the well-being of society, especially for those who need it most, as well as increasing public trust in zakat amil institutions. In the implementation of management of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, amil yap institutions play a role as managers and those who don't need answers For collect, manage, and allocate these funds. Institutions can form institutions established by the government and established institutions in a way self-help by the Community (Handayani, 2020).

One study uses mark net assets (ROA) as a moderating variable to determine how dividend policy impacts on value of companies in the conventional banking sector.

Study the show that net asset mark (ROA) affects company mark in a significant way, and dividend policy There can be no moderate connection between ROA and company value. In addition, ROA has been used as a moderating variable in influencing capital structure towards company mark at level (Permatasari et al., 2019).

Size of the company is very influential disclosure of Islamic Social Reporting (ISR) in sharia commercial banks. Research conducted use method study statistics and analysis panel data regression shows that company size (company size) has an impact on ISR reporting of Islamic banks in Indonesia. Company size is defined as total assets companies, and study findings show that Islamic banks with more total assets big will influence IS disclosure. AAOIFI (Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions) created ISR index, which is against measuring implementation performance of social Sharia banking. This index consists of a number of indicators CSR standards. Study others also show that company size, capital adequacy, risk financing, and company stability to The profitability of Islamic banks in Indonesia can also be achieved measured and analyzed (Baiquni, 2017).

Collection of Zakat and Waqf funds (ZISWAF), one of their sources of funds that refers to wadiah principles guaranteed by law and MUI fatwa, has a positive impact on the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) of sharia banks. These funds can be used to launch new products, such as mudharabah, so increase Islamic bank income. Return on assets (ROA) also has a positive effect on CAR. ROA is a size calculated profit from total income divided by total assets. Sharia bank with high ROA will own better performance and have the ability to increase CAR. Wadiah bonuses also have a positive impact against CAR. Prize bonus is part of Sharia bank income received by customers. If it's a high gift bonus, then Islamic banks will have more performance well, which in turn will CAR will increase (Helena Purba & Marjulin, 2022).

Research purposes is For research How receipt of Zakat, Waqf and Sadaqah (ZISWAF) funds as well as Return on Assets (ROA) and Wadiah Bonuses have an impact on the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) in Islamic banking in Indonesia. This study will also use firm size as variable moderation in the period 2015.Q1 to in 2023.Q3.

LITERATURE REVIEW

ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds (zakat, infaq, alms, waqf)

Zakat is treasure in certain amounts issued by the owner as cleaner himself and his property from everything that pollutes it, as well as expecting the blessing of Allah SWT. Zakat is also an effort to realize social concern in real life. The basic word (masdar) from the word zakat comes from the word zaka, which means growing, holy, blessing, and developing. Infaq originates from the word nafaqa, which means "to have passed, passed, or finished. However, infaq means give part of treasure to others for free. Therefore that's it, infaq is donate, give sustenance, or spend something to others for help they fulfill their needs, like food and drink, with sincere and only because of Allah SWT. By etymology, "almsgiving" comes from the word "shadaqohyang", which means something a gift given by someone to other people spontaneously and voluntarily without limited in time or amount. By terminology, alms is interpreted as giving someone to the right person accept it in a way sincere with hope only blessings of Allah SWT (Wulpiah, 2017).

Return On Assets

Investors and finance analysts often use return on assets (ROA), as ratio finances used To measure how much effective a company is in producing profit from each unit of asset it owns. By simple, ROA can be calculated by sharing the company's clean profit with the total value of the assets it owns. Asset value (ROA) can help investors and finance analysts evaluate the efficiency of a company in producing profit. Second, ROA can help a company in finding assets that are not productive or are not efficient in producing profit. However, ROA also has a certain amount of weakness. Firstly, ROA does not take into account risk factors in producing profit, and secondly, ROA does not take into account differences in company capital structure. In interpreting ROCE, ROA does not take into account factors. Return On Assets (ROA) Return On Assets (ROA) or ratio return on total assets is one of the forms of ratio profitability. Ratio profitability is the company's ability to obtain profit from its business (Sunyoto, 2013). Following is formula For looking for return on assets

$$\text{ROA} = (\text{Net Income} : \text{Total Assets}) \times 100\%$$

Bonus prizes

Prize bonus is a bonus given as incentive to custodian of wadiah funds, which is a product from Islamic finance institutions. Prize bonuses can be in the form of cash and distributed to the custodian account of wadiah funds. Writing "wadiah" in context This originates from the word "trust" which means trust or obligation For regulate and mandate party funds third For channeled, esp from savings. Prize bonus can be in the form of a top bonus balance lowest, top bonus base daily average balance, or top bonus base balance daily Giving gift bonuses done with the objective of increasing awareness of customers to the importance of saving and investing in sharia banks. Prize bonuses are also available to increase trust customers towards Islamic banks and improve the loyalty of customers in saving and investing in sharia banks. In synthesis, gift bonuses are a form of incentives provided to customers as rewards on their savings do it at a sharia bank. Giving gift bonuses is done with the objective of increasing customers' awareness of the importance of saving and investing in Islamic banks and increasing customers' trust towards Islamic banks (Sardiana & Zulfison, 2016) .

Capital adequacy ratio

The Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is a ratio used To evaluate a deep bank's ability to withhold loss and fulfill financial obligations. CAR is calculated with method divide total bank capital by total assets at risk, then multiplied by 100% to get percentage. In CAR, Tier 1 Capital consists on shares ordinary and profitable retained, which is considered as highest capital quality Because it can withhold losses without causing the bank to become insolvent. Tier 2 Capital consists of debts that are not guaranteed and other instruments, which are considered not reliable enough however can withhold small loss. CAR is used as yardstick measuring the strength of bank finances and capabilities withhold loss. The higher the CAR, then the bank is considered own more abilities Good at withholding losses and fulfilling financial obligations. CAR is also used as a stress test For many banks, to determine How many a lot of money the bank needs to face various risks on various sectors and fronts faced. CAR is also used as standard to determine whether the bank has sufficient capital to withhold losses and fulfill financial obligations. CAR is regulated by the Central Bank and varies by country. In Indonesia, commercial banks must have a CAR of at least 9% In synthesis, the CAR is something

important ratio For evaluating deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfilling financial obligations. CAR is used as yardstick measuring the strength of bank finance and use as standard To determine whether the bank has Enough capital To withhold loss and fulfill financial obligations (Sofyan, 2021).

Following is the formula to look for the capital adequacy ratio

$$\text{CAR} = (\text{Tier 1 Capital} + \text{Tier 2 Capital}) / \text{Risk-Weighted Assets}$$

Firm size

The definition of Firm Size is something size, scale, or describing variables big or small company based on a number of terms, such as total assets, log size, market value, shares, total sales, total income, total capital, etc. Firm size available can be measured with various marks such as total assets, amount sales, average sales, and total assets. Company size This is used to represent company financial characteristics, such as company ability in accessing financial resources, company capabilities in producing income, etc. (Luly, 2020).

Influence receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds with Capital Adequacy ratio (H1)

Influence ZISWAF Fund Receipts to Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is something purposeful research To test How ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds can be received influence deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill financial obligations. This study uses secondary data from Islamic banking finance reports and uses a quantitative approach to analyze the influence of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on CAR. Research results show that receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds does not have a significant influence on CAR. This matters because Islamic banking is in use of more capital be careful and focused on guarding bank liquidity, so No there is a significant influence on CAR a company's economic efficiency and success approach can be used to determine the connection between receipt of zakat funds (Zakat) and Return on Assets (ROA) (Muharramah, 2017).

Effect of Return on assets with capital adequacy ratio (H2)

The effect of Return on Assets (ROA) on the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is something purposeful research To test how ROA can influence deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill financial obligations. ROA is calculated with the method share profit clean with total assets owned by the bank, then multiplied with 100% to get percentage. Research results show that ROA has a positive and significant influence on CAR. The higher the ROA, the higher the CAR. ROA can increase deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finances, so can increase CAR (Ruri Kurniasari, 2022).

Effect of Wadiah Bonus with Capital adequacy ratio (H3)

The effect of the Wadiah Bonus on the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is something purposeful research To test how about wadiah bonus can influence deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill financial obligations. Prize bonus is a form of incentives provided to customers as rewards on their savings do it at a sharia bank. Research results show that gift bonuses themselves have a positive influence on CAR. Prize bonus can increase deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation

finances, so can increase CAR (Zumara, 2021).

Influence of Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on the Capital adequacy ratio is moderated with firm size (H4)

Influence Acceptance of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds towards Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is moderated with Firm Size is something purposeful research To test How ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds can be received influence deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill financial obligations, as well How company size can influence the. Research results show that ZISWAF fund receipts have a positive influence on CAR, however the influence can vary depending on company size. ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds can be received increase deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finances, so can increase CAR. However, company size can influence the method of reducing deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfilling obligation finances, so it can reduce CAR (Hayunah, 2018).

The influence of Return on assets on the capital adequacy ratio is moderated with firm size (H5)

The influence of Return On Assets (ROA) on the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is moderated with Firm Size is something purposeful research To test how ROA can influence deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill financial obligations, as well How company size can influence influence the. Research results show that ROA has a positive influence on CAR, however the influence can vary depending on company size. ROA can increase deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill financial obligations, so can increase CAR. However, company size can influence the method of reducing deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfilling obligation finances, so it can reduce CAR (Novrianti, 2021).

The effect of the Wadiah Bonus on The capita adequacy ratio is moderated with firm size (H6)

The influence of the Wadiah Bonus on the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is moderated with Firm Size is something purposeful research To test how about wadiah bonus can influence deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill financial obligations, as well How company size can influence the. Research results show that gift bonuses themselves influence positively towards CAR, however the influence can vary depending on company size. Prize bonus can increase deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill financial obligations, so can increase CAR. However, company size can influence the method of reducing deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfilling obligation finances, so it can reduce CAR (Mulyadhi, 2020).

The influence receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, return on assets, and wadiah bonuses on capital adequacy ratio (H7)

Influence ZISWAF Fund Receipts, Return On Assets (ROA), and Wadiah Bonus to Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is something purposeful research To test How receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, ROA, and Wadiah bonuses can influence deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligations finance. Research results show that receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds

is not a significant influence on CAR. ROA has a positive influence on CAR, however the influence can vary depending on company size. Prize bonus own positive influence towards CAR, however the influence can vary depending on the size of the company (Khusnul Imamah & Achmad Munif, 2018).

Following is connection between independent variable and dependent variable

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

Research methods

Method used in study This is a quantitative method. Data used in study This is secondary data that comes from a report accessed annually via the Financial Services Authority website. Population used is company sector finance in 2015.Q1 – 2023 which is listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (BEI) with a sample taking technique using purposive sampling technique (Novianto, 2021).

Data analysis methods used in research This is Panel Data Regression Model and Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA). Test interactions or often called Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) using a sustaining analytics approach sample integrity and deliver base To give influence to moderator variables (Kusnadi & Tandika, 2019).

Following is inner model equations analysis panel data regression:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + e_i$$

Where:

Y = Capital adequacy ratio

α = constant

β = Coefficient Regression

X1 = Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds

X2 = Return on assets

X3 = Gift bonus

e_i = Error

Testing hypothesis in research This use regression analysis with variable moderation Moderating Regression Analysis (MRA), eq the regression contains element interaction with equality formula as following

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 Z + \beta_5 X_1 * Z + \beta_6 X_2 * Z + \beta_7 X_3 * Z + e_i$$

Where: Y = Capital adequacy ratio

α = Constant

β = Coefficient Regression

X1 = Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds

X2 = Return on assets

X3 = Gift bonus

Z = Firm Size

X1*Z = Interaction multiplication between receipt of funds and Firm Size

X2*Z = Interaction multiplication between Return On assets and Firm Size

X3*Z = Interaction multiplication between Wadiah Bonus and Firm Size

e_i = Error

Research results

Descriptive analysis

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

	X1	X2	X3	Y	Z
Mean	25082.01	0.8354	27378.27	26	16.65104
Maximum	669879.0	4.08	558636.0	149.58	19.58000
Minimum	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	10.16	14.12000
Std. Dev.	87500.44	1.182268	64369.17	18.96131	1.474160
Observations	115	115	115	115	115

Based on table 1, it can be known that the study sample size is 115 samples at 5 Sharia Banks (Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah) 2018Q1-2023Q3. On variables Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds (X1) based on results statistics descriptive information contained in Table 1 can be known that variable Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds own average value 25082.01, maximum value 669879.0, minimum value 0.000000 and standard deviation 87500.44.

The variable Return on assets (X2) is based on results statistics. The descriptive descriptions contained in Table 1 can be known that the Return on Assets variable has average value 0.8354, maximum value 4.08, minimum value 0.000000 and standard deviation 1.182268.

On the Wadiah Bonus variable (X3) based on results statistics The descriptive descriptions contained in Table 1 can be known that Wadiah Bonus variables have average value 27378.27, maximum value 558636.0, minimum value 0.000000 and standard deviation 64369.17.

On variables Firm Size (Z) moderation based on results statistics The descriptive descriptions contained in Table 1 can be known that the variable Firm Size moderation has average value 16.65104, maximum value 19.58000, minimum value 14.12000 and standard deviation 1.474160.

Ratio (Y) variable is based on results statistics The descriptive descriptions contained in Table 1 can be known that variable Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds own average value 26, maximum value 149.58, minimum value

10, 16 and standard deviation 18.96131.

Election panel data regression

The selection of the panel data regression model is stages analysis To determine the best method between Common Effect, Fixed Effect or Random Effect

Test Chow

This test was carried out to find out the best model between the Common Effect Model (CEM) and the Fixed Effect Model (FEM).

Table 2. Chow test

Effects Test	Statistics	df	Prob.
Cross-section F	12.83774	(4,106)	0.0000
Chi-square cross-section	30.416868	4	0.0000

Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Based on table 2, the results of the Chow test show that the cross-section chi-square probability value is $0.0000 < 0.05$. So it can be said that in this test, the best model to use is the Fixed Effect Model (FEM).

Hausman test

This Hausman test aims to select the best model between the Fixed Effect Model (FEM) and the Random Effect Model (REM).

Table 3. Hausman Test Results

Correlated Random Effects-Hausman Test
Equation: Untitled
Cross-section random effects test

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistics	Chi-Sq. df	Prob.
Random cross-section	54.34483	3	0.0000

Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

From table 3 above, it can be seen that the results of the Hausman test show a probability value of $0.0000 < 0.05$. So it can be said that in this test, the best model to use is the Fixed Effect Model (FEM)

Test Assumptions classic

Normality test

Table 4. Normality Test

Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Based on Figure 4 above, it shows that the probability value is 0.527693, which means the probability value is above 0.05 ($0.527693 > 0.05$). So it can be concluded that the data in this study is normally distributed.

Multicollinearity test

Table 5. Multicollinearity test

	X1	X2	X3
X1	1.000000	0.034521	0.367353
X2	0.032459	1.000000	0.464378
X3	0.026435	0.426433	1.000000

Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Based on table 5, the results of the multicollinearity test can be seen if the correlation values between the independent variables are all below 0.85. This means that if the research data does not contain multicollinearity between independent variables.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 6. Heteroscedasticity Test

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
X1	-0.004341	0.004917	-0.882817	0.3884
X2	63.10679	104.8350	0.601963	0.5543
X3	-0.001706	0.003214	-0.530934	0.6016

Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Based on table 7, the results of the heteroscedasticity test show that the resulting

probability values are 2 variables that have values above 0.05 and one other variable below 0.05. A regression model is said to be free from heteroscedasticity if it has a probability value above 0.05. So it can be concluded that in the regression model used in this research there is no heteroscedasticity.

Panel Data Regression Analysis

The following is a panel data regression analysis using the best model, namely the Fixed Effect Model regression:

Table 7. Analysis of Fixed Effect Panel Data Regression model

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
C	-120202.7	253902.3	-3.445388	0.0000
X1	2407.537	2453.011	1.043056	0.2463
X2	0.542365	0.456493	4.45345	0.7547
X3	0.053508	0.574536	-0.84543	0.4436
Z	35355.29	15646.70	4.453492	0.0000

Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA)

Moderating variables can be interpreted as variables that can strengthen or weaken the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The following are the test results from the moderation regression analysis:

Table 8. Analysis test regression moderation

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
C	-334558.3	35345.5	-2.456453	0.0013
X1	6434.345	45634.23	0.145433	0.5124
X2	-13.03455	4.34234	-2.23425	0.0012
X3	4.45345	1.34522	2.46567	0.0154
Z	34543.34	13425.54	2.64544	0.0004
X1Z	-243.3454	2678.675	-0.34454	0.6542
X2Z	0.67854	0.37535	3.45434	0.0012
X3Z	-0.785643	0.345456	-2.75654	0.0157

Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Statistical tests

T test

T test, for test is in a way Partial dependent variable has a significant effect on independent variable. Apart from that, it is also used to know is the influence of each independent variable to the dependent variable tested at a significance level of 0.05 or with level 95% confidence and rate 5% error.

Table 9. T test

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
C	-233435.7	335244.4	-3.352576	0.0016
X1	2365.456	45644.10	0.134676	0.8345
X2	-12.35323	2.125256	-3.135433	0.0013
X3	4.363654	1.235476	2.326435	0.0134
Z	42355.65	23563.45	3.454536	0.0004
X1Z	-261.7342	2544.456	-0.135645	0.4535
X2Z	0.463522	0.573134	3.356445	0.0014
X3Z	-0.432532	0.352352	-2.856433	0.0145

Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Based on the t test (partial). done author on the study This can be known that the results obtained from the t test ie as follows:

1. Hypothesis 1 (H1): Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds own influence to the Capital Adequacy Ratio. With mark coefficient 45644.10 and probability value 0.8345 which means bigger than significant mark 0.05 or 5%. That matter shows that Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds influenced on the Capital adequacy ratio at Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah for the period 2018 Q1-2023 Q3.
2. Hypothesis 2 (H2): Return on assets has influence to the Capital adequacy ratio. With mark coefficient 2.125256 and probability value 0.0013 which means bigger than significant mark 0.05 or 5%. That matter shows that Return on Assets has an effect on the Capital adequacy ratio at Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah for the period 2018 Q1-2023 Q3.
3. Hypothesis 3 (H3): Bous Wadiah has influence to the Capital adequacy ratio. With mark coefficient 1.235476 and probability value 0.0134 which means smaller than significant mark 0.05 or 5%. That matter shows that the Wadiah Bonus has an effect on the Capital adequacy ratio at Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah for the period 2018 Q1-2023 Q3.
4. Hypothesis 4 (H4): Receipts of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds influence the Capital adequacy ratio is moderated by Firm Size. With mark coefficient 2544.456 and probability value 0.4535 which means bigger than significant mark 0.05 or 5%. That matter shows that Firm Size is not capable of moderate influence receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on the Capital adequacy ratio at Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah for the period 2018 Q1-2023 Q3.
5. Hypothesis 5 (H5): Return on assets has an effect the Capital adequacy ratio is moderated by Firm Size. With mark coefficient 0.573134 and probability value

0.0014 which means smaller than significant mark 0.05 or 5%. That matter shows that Firm Size is capable of moderate the influence of Return on assets on the Capital adequacy ratio at Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah for the period 2018 Q1-2023 Q3.

6. Hypothesis 6 (H6): Wadiah Bonus has an effect the Capital adequacy ratio is moderated by Firm Size. With mark coefficient 0.352352 and probability value 0.0145 which means smaller than significant mark 0.05 or 5%. That matter shows that Firm Size is capable moderate The influence of the Wadiah Bonus on the Capital adequacy ratio at Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah for the period 2018 Q1-2023 Q3.

F test

F test, used For test is in a way simultaneous independent variables have a significant influence on the dependent variable. Following are F test results.

Table 10. F Test Results

Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000
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Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

F test in research This use mark significance 0.05 or 5% with criteria If mark significance $F < 0.05$ then the recession coefficient is worthy of use. F test results in table 10 above show mark F significance is 0.000000, the value is smaller than mark significance namely 0.05. So that it can be concluded that Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, Return on assets. Prize bonus in a way simultaneously own influence to the Capital adequacy ratio.

Coefficient Test Determination

Coefficient Determination, used to show how much contribution the independent variable has in the regression model in explaining the variation of the dependent variable.

Table 11. Coefficient test results determination

Adjusted squared	R-0.23646 3
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Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Based on Table 11 panel data regression test results on Capital adequacy ratio as dependent variable, shows that Adjusted R2 value is 0.236463. This matter can be interpreted that of 23.64% the Capital adequacy ratio variable can be explained by Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, Return on assets, and

wadiah bonus. Meanwhile the rest can be explained with other variables outside the regression model

DISCUSSION

Influence receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds to the capital adequacy ratio

Based on table 9 results testing show mark probability Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds equal to 0.8345 which means bigger than 0.05. The test results also show positive direction with mark coefficient 2365.456 and t-statistic 0.134676. So that shows that receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds No own significant influence to the Capital adequacy ratio. So the hypothesis is proposed by the researcher namely H1: Effect of Gross NPF on Acceptance of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds rejected.

Research results This is in line with a study previously conducted by Muharramah (2017) which shows that receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds does not have a significant influence on CAR. This matters because Islamic banking is in use of more capital be careful and focused on guarding bank liquidity, so No there is a significant influence on CAR a company's economic efficiency and success approach can be used to determine the connection between receipt of zakat funds (Zakat) and Return on Assets (ROA).

Effect of Return on assets on Capital adequacy ratio

Based on table 9 testing results show mark the probability of Return on assets is 0.0013, which means smaller than 0.05. The test results also show negative direction with mark coefficient -12.35323 and t-statistic -3.135433. So that shows that Return on assets has a negative effect on the Capital adequacy ratio. So the hypothesis is proposed by the researcher namely H2: The influence of Return on assets on the Capital adequacy ratio is accepted.

Research results In line with research previously conducted by Kurniasari (2022) that ROA has a positive and significant influence on CAR. The higher the ROA, the higher the CAR. ROA can increase deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill financial obligations, so can increase CAR.

The effect of gift bonuses on the capital adequacy ratio

Based on table 9 testing results show mark the probability of the Wadiah Bonus is 0.0134 which means smaller than 0.05. The test results also show positive direction with mark coefficient 4.363654 and t-statistic 2.326435. So that shows that the Wadiah Bonus has a positive effect on the Capital adequacy ratio. So the hypothesis is proposed by the researcher namely H3: The influence of the Wadiah Bonus on the Capital adequacy ratio is accepted.

Research results in line with study previously conducted by Zumara (2021) that gift bonuses themselves influence positively towards CAR. Prize bonus can increase deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill financial obligations, so can increase CAR.

Influence receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds to Capital adequacy ratio Moderated with the capital adequacy ratio

Based on table 9 results testing show mark probability interaction between Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds with profitability equal to 0.4535 which means more bigger than 0.05. The test results also show negative direction with mark coefficient -261.7342 and t-statistic -0.135645. These results show that Firm Size cannot strengthen the influence between Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds with Firm size. So the hypothesis is proposed by the researcher namely H4: Firm Size is capable of moderate receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on the capital adequacy ratio is rejected.

Research results This is in line with a study previously conducted by Sardiana & Zulfison (2016) that ZISWAF fund receipts have a positive influence on CAR, however the influence can vary depending on company size. ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds can be received increase deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finances, so can increase CAR. However, company size can influence the method of reducing deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfilling financial obligations, so it can lower CAR.

The influence of return on assets on the capital adequacy ratio is moderated with firm size

Based on table 9 testing results show mark probability interaction between Return on assets and profitability of 0.0014 which means smaller than 0.05. The test results also show positive direction with mark coefficient 0.463522 and t-statistic 3.356445. These results show that Firm Size can strengthen the influence between Income Mudharabah and Firm size. So the hypothesis is proposed by the researcher namely H5: Firm Size is capable of moderate Income Mudharabah to Acceptance of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds accepted.

Research results This is in line with a study previously conducted by Novrianti (2021) that ROA has a positive influence on CAR, however the influence can vary depending on company size. ROA can increase deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill financial obligations, so can increase CAR. However, company size can influence the method of reducing deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfilling financial obligations, so it can lower CAR.

The effect of gift bonuses on the capital adequacy ratio is moderated with firm size

Based on table 9 results testing show mark probability interaction between the Wadiah Bonus and profitability of 0.0145 which means smaller than 0.05. The test results also show positive direction with mark coefficient -0.432532 and t-statistic -2.856433. These results show that Firm Size can strengthen the influence between Wadiah Bonus and Firm size. So the hypothesis is proposed by the researcher namely H6: Firm Size is capable of moderate bonuses wadiah to the Capital adequacy ratio is accepted.

Research results This is in line with study previously carried out by Mulyadhi (2020) that the wadiah bonus itself has a positive influence on CAR, however the influence can vary depending on the size of the company. Prize bonus can increase deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill financial obligations, so can increase CAR. However, company size can influence the method of reducing deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfilling financial obligations, so it can lower CAR.

Influence Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, Return on

assets, and wadiah bonuses in a way simultaneous to the Capital adequacy ratio

Based on calculations in table 10 it can be concluded that the variables Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, Return on assets, and Wadiah Bonus have a significant influence on the capital adequacy ratio. This matter caused Because mark significance $0.000000 < 0.05$. These results show that Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, Return on assets, and Wadiah Bonus have an influence in a simultaneous way to Capital adequacy ratio. So the hypothesis is proposed by the researcher namely H7: Gross NPF, Income Mudharabah, and Wadiah Bonus simultaneous to Acceptance of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds accepted. On coefficients determination or R Square results value 0.236463. Interpretation from the number shows that contribution from the fourth free variable is amounting to 23.64% and the remainder namely 76.36% influenced by other factors so that To do further study more can use other independent variables (Ramadhani, Sukardi, et al., 2022) (Murniyasih et al., 2022) (Ramadhani, Wahyuningsih, et al., 2022) (Ramadhani et al., 2024) .

CONCLUSION

Research results This shows that Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds affect CAR significantly. which means that if mark Reception increases then CAR will decrease low, and vice versa. In other words, Return on assets has a significant negative impact on CAR; if return on assets is generated high, that will produce CAR decreases, and vice versa. Next, during interaction variable moderation, Firm size is not able to control the influence of a Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on sector CAR finances in 2018–2023. Additionally, firm size cannot control the influence of return on assets on mark company sector finances in 2018–2023.

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